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STUDY OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE OF ICICI AND IOB

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Abstract

The study aims to understand the organizational structure followed in a private sector bank and a public sector bank. The structure should normally follow the vision and strategy of the business; else it would be a case of the tail wagging the dog. Changing the structure and doing little else may not result in significant change in the way of working. Changes in structure may need to be accompanied by changes in systems and processes, role definition, interfaces within the organization and the external environment, etc. A questionnaire was prepared based on the various parameters describing the organizational structure. The questionnaire was floated among the higher officials in the two organizations. A descriptive research design has been adopted in the study. Purposive sampling/ stratified random sampling has been used and the sample size is 20. We can conclude that a public sector organization has more formalized structure than a private organization. Secondly, a public sector organization has more centralized structure than a private organization.

Keywords: formalization, centralization, strategy, alignment, organizational culture.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations use various structural alternatives to help them achieve their purpose and goals. It is not possible to see the internal structure of an organization the way we might see its manufacturing tools, offices or products. Although we might see employees going about their duties, performing different tasks, and working in all different locations but to understand the structure is a really a complex process. Nearly every firm needs to undergo structural reorganization at some point to help meet new challenges. Structural changes are needed to reflect new strategies or respond to changes in other contingency factors for example environment, technology, size and life cycle and culture.

Organizational structure

There are three key components in the definition of organization structure:

- Organizational structure designates formal reporting relationships, including the number of levels in the hierarchy and the span of control of managers and supervisors.
- Organization structure identifies the grouping together of individuals into departments and of departments into the total organization.
- Organization structure includes the design of systems to ensure effective communication, coordination and integration of efforts across departments.

These three elements of structure pertain to both vertical and horizontal aspects of organizing. For example, the first two elements are the structural framework, which is the vertical hierarchy. The third element pertains to pattern of interactions among organizational employees. An ideal structure encourages employees to provide horizontal information and coordination where and when it is needed.

Structure could be a key factor to survive and grow in an environment where speed, service, architecting customized solutions, flexibility and time-to-market are important factors. Organizations need to align various elements—such as business strategy, people capability, systems and processes—to evolve a structure that will facilitate achievement of objectives. Organization structure needs to facilitate achievement of business objectives.

The organizational structure can be described on the basis of four dimensions- centralization, formalization, size and vertical complexity.

- a) **Centralization:** Centralization reflects the concentration of power or decision making authority in an organization. It is comprised of two sub dimensions—participation in decision making and authority hierarchy (Hage & Aiken, 1967). Participation in decision making reflects concentration of decision making power with respect to departmental issues like policy making, hiring, and promotion. Authority hierarchy reflects concentration of decision making power with respect to performing one's job. Thus, less participation and greater authority hierarchy indicate increasing centralization.

Concentration of power and the absence of participation could allow economic benefits to amass disproportionality to those at the top of the hierarchical ladder (where power typically accrues), leaving others behind. This should be seen as less fair than allocation patterns likely to evolve under broader participation.

- b) **Formalization:** Formalization describes the extent to which explicit operating rules, procedures, instructions, and communications are written down (Pugh, Hickson, Hinings, & Turner, 1968). Formalized systems are those in which explicit rules and regulations dictate how things happen in organizational settings.

In highly formalized systems, the processes by which decisions are made (influencing procedural justice) are dictated by the formal operating procedures of the organization. Similarly, what outcomes are appropriate to specific situations (distributive justice) are codified as well. Interestingly, the scope of formalized systems can be exceedingly broad, extending to the interpersonal interactions among employees, as well as between employees and customers. This consistency of rules—as they relate to procedures, outcomes, and interpersonal interactions—should enhance individuals' confidence that they are being treated in a fashion similar to others in equivalent situations, and thus, result in higher justice perceptions.

- c) **Size:** Organizational size represents our third structural component. We operationalize size as the total number of employees making up an organization.
- d) **Vertical Complexity:** Vertical complexity represents another important structural dimension of organizations. Vertical complexity denotes the number of levels in an organizational hierarchy. It has been shown to be positively associated with organizational size. large organizations also tend to be complex organizations

Organization culture

Culture of the organization plays a key role in determining a structure that would suit. The organization stance towards participation and risk-taking will have an impact on the decision pertaining to number of levels and delegation of authority. Congruence between culture and structure is important.

SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH

One bank from each sector i.e public sector as well as private sector has been taken as pilot. Among public sector banks Indian Overseas Bank has been selected and among private sector banks, the selected bank is ICICI. The scope of the research is to study the organizational structure being followed in these banks and discussing the various positive and negative aspects of each structure.

BRIEF PROFILES OF THE ORGANIZATIONS SELECTED

ICICI Bank Limited

In 1955, seven years since India had become independent, it was also the time to rebuild the nation and industrialization was the only way forward. It was at this time that with the initiative of the World Bank and the Indian government, that the Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India, ICICI, was formed.

Sixteen years later in 1971, to give a new lease of life to its rather nondescript existence, the corporation hired a batch of young business graduates. Among them, was 24-year-old Kundapur Vaman Kamath; fresh out of management school in Ahmedabad. In time, Kamath redefined banking in India and become a legend in his own right. Mangalore-born Kamath joined the Project Finance Division of ICICI as a management trainee in 1971. A quick learner, Kamath demonstrated his entrepreneurial skills early in his career and his sheer talent caught the attention of the then chairman of ICICI, N Vaghul. Kamath set-up new businesses in leasing, venture capital, credit rating as well as handling general management position. Taking his responsibilities a step further, he implemented ICICI's computerization programme, which in later years would give ICICI a huge competitive advantage.

By 1994, the impact of the economic reforms initiated by the Narasimha Rao government were beginning to show, albeit rather slowly. The same year, ICICI Limited had set up its subsidiary -- ICICI Bank. Two years later, in 1996, Vaghul's protégé KV Kamath rejoined ICICI as its new Managing Director and CEO. Kamath immediately initiated strategic initiatives and structural changes across the ICICI Group that helped redraw its boundaries.

MD & CEO, ICICI Bank, KV Kamath says, "An organization, which is 40 years old, you need to move some people into some positions, in which you think they would be better and that's what was on top of my mind."

Kamath's immediate priority after his return was to create new operations in the organization and more importantly, to tap new markets. He introduced flexibility in the bank's functions and shaped them to respond to new market reactions.

ICICI Bank and ICICI, along with other ICICI group companies, were operating as a "virtual universal bank", offering a wide range of financial products and services. The merger of ICICI and two of its subsidiaries with ICICI Bank has combined two organizations with complementary strengths and products and similar processes and operating architecture.

The merger has combined the large capital base of ICICI with the strong deposit raising capability of ICICI Bank, giving ICICI Bank improved ability to increase its market share in banking fees and commissions, while lowering the overall cost of funding through access to lower-cost retail deposits. ICICI Bank would now be able to fully leverage the strong corporate relationships that ICICI has built, seamlessly providing the whole range of financial products and services to corporate clients.

In September 1999, within three years of taking over as the Managing Director and CEO of ICICI, KV Kamath drew up aggressive plans for growth. That year, ICICI Ltd got listed on the New York Stock Exchange, NYSE, the first ever Indian financial institution to go the American Depository Receipts, ADR route.

Post the listing with the NYSE; ICICI had ambitious expansion plans and this time, it was through inorganic growth.

The year 2002 was the landmark year for ICICI, the board of directors of ICICI and ICICI Bank approved the merger of the parent company ICICI and subsidiaries like ICICI Personal Financial Services Ltd and ICICI Capital Services Ltd, with yet another subsidiary ICICI Bank. The entire banking and financial operations of the group was brought under one roof. It was a reverse merger and quite rare in corporate India, where a parent company merged with its subsidiary and adopted the latter's identity.

IOB Limited

Established in 1937, Indian Overseas Bank (IOB) is a leading bank based in Chennai, India. IOB had the distinction of simultaneously commencing operations in three branches at Karaikudi, Chennai, and Yangon (Myanmar). Since IOB aimed to encourage overseas banking and foreign exchange operations, it soon opened its branches in Penang and Singapore. Today, Indian Overseas Bank boasts of a vast domain in banking sector with over 1400 domestic branches and 6 branches overseas.

IOB was the first bank to venture into consumer credit, as it introduced the popular Personal Loan scheme. In 1964, the Bank started computerization in the areas of inter-branch reconciliation and provident fund accounts. Indian Overseas Bank was one of the 14 major banks which were nationalized in 1969. After nationalization, the Bank emphasized on opening its branches in rural parts of India. In 1979, IOB opened a Foreign Currency Banking Unit in the free trade zone in Colombo.

The Bank's IT department has developed software, which is used by its 1200 branches to provide online banking to customers. Indian Overseas Bank also has a network of about 500 ATMs throughout India. Its International VISA Debit Card is accepted at all ATMs belonging to the Cash Tree and NFS networks. IOB also offers Internet Banking; it's one of the banks that the Govt. of India has approved for online payment of taxes.

Indian Overseas Bank offers investment options like Mutual Funds and Shares. It provides a wide range of consumer and commercial banking services, including Savings Account, Current Account, Depository Services, VISA Cards, Credit Cards, Debit Cards, Online Banking, Any Branch Banking, Home Loans, NRI Account, Agricultural Loans, Payment of Bills / Taxes, Provident Fund Scheme, Forex Collection Services, Retail Loans, etc.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mittal & Batra (2015) the study of second-order model enhances the understanding of the structure of service quality for retail banking services in India. The most important dimension was tangibles, especially the physical environment which facilitates efficient delivery of service.

Kaur & Sharma (2013) the employees of public sector banks have shown a higher perception for rational goal model as against the human relations model by the private as well as the foreign bank employees.

Gaubha (2012) the industry might have many stumbling blocks in the 'Road Ahead' but when ever encountered with such blocks in the past it has used them as a stepping stone & has always 'Transformed' itself (for the better) and 'Evolved' as a winner.

Padmavathy et al (2012) revealed five dimensions for customer relationship management effectiveness (CRME). Reliability was found to positively affect customer satisfaction and to have direct association with customer loyalty and both customer satisfaction and loyalty-influenced cross-buying.

Mondal & Ghosh (2012) indicates that the relationships between the performance of a bank's intellectual capital, and financial performance indicators, namely profitability and productivity, are varied. It also suggests that banks' intellectual capital is vital for their competitive advantage.

Barnabas (2010) suggests that superior personnel related and goal setting autonomy at boundary spanning levels have positive market orientation as well as performance implications. Formalization while negatively impacting market orientation did not directly impact performance.

Kumar & Gulati (2009) reveal that high efficiency does not stand for high effectiveness in the Indian public sector banks (PSB) industry. A positive and strong correlation between effectiveness and performance measures has been noted.

Bajaj (2009) similarities/dissimilarities between two cultures were not analyzed before the decision to acquire was taken. It also found that as the two banks had very different cultures and needed high degree of integration, threat of cultural conflict was very high.

Ray (2007) many of the banks are, indeed, too large in various years and the study found that often a bank is operating in the region of diminishing returns to scale but is not a candidate for break up.

Kamath (2007) confirms the existence of vast differences in the performance of Indian banks in different segments, and there is also an improvement in the overall performance over the study period. There is an evident bias in favour of the performance of foreign banks compared with domestic banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objectives:

- To study the organizational structure being followed in IOB and ICICI.
- To discuss the various positive and negative aspects of each organizational structure.

Research Design: The descriptive research design is adopted in the study.

Sampling technique: Purposive sampling/ stratified random sampling has been adopted.

Sample size (N) = The sample size is 20.

Research tool and techniques: A questionnaire was prepared based on the various parameters describing the organizational structure. The questionnaire was floated among the higher officials in the two organizations.

STRUCTURE OF ICICI BANK LIMITED

The organizational structure of ICICI is dynamic, constantly evolving and responsive to changes both in internal as well as external environment. Its structure is designed to support its business goals and is flexible while at the same time ensuring effective control, supervision and consistency in standards across business groups.

Level of formalization: Since the organization is adaptable to dynamic environment, it has a less formalized structure. Rules and regulations are not very strict and can be changed on the basis of market demand. This organization is able to change both internally as well as externally.

Level of centralization: The operations are more decentralized in this organization as the branches have adequate level of flexibility, within a defined level of control framework to ensure faster customer service and decision making.

Size: ICICI Bank is India's second-largest bank. It had just over 73,362 employees in 2009 demonstrating their unique technology-driven, productivity-focused business model. The bank has 1,438 branches and is in the process of opening 580 branches during the current fiscal to March 2010.

ICICI has started reorganizing its business by focusing on new areas and changing the portfolios of some of its new senior executives. Managing director and chief executive officer Chanda Kochhar has announced the restructuring exercise and listed the new focus areas through two emails sent to the bank's employees.

Changing focus: Chanda Kochhar says the bank periodically reviews its organizational structure to ensure it is in tune with evolving operating environment and aligned to achieve defined objectives as well as capitalize on the emerging opportunities.

ICICI Bank seeks to build in all its employees a total commitment towards exceptional standards of performance and productivity, adaptability to changing organizational needs and the demands of the business environment and a willingness to learn and acquire new capabilities. ICICI Bank believes in defining clear performance parameters for employees and empowering them to achieve their goals. This has helped to create a culture of high performance across the organization.

The organization structure is divided into five principal groups – Retail Banking, Wholesale Banking, Project Finance & Special Assets Management, International Business and Corporate Centre.

The Retail Banking Group comprises ICICI Bank's retail assets business including various retail credit products, retail liabilities (including our own deposit accounts as well as distribution of third part liability products) and rural micro-banking.

The Wholesale Banking Group comprises ICICI Bank's corporate banking business including credit products and banking services, with separate dedicated groups for large corporates, Government and public sector entities and emerging corporates. Treasury, structured finance and credit portfolio management also form part of this group.

The Project Finance Group comprises our project finance operations for infrastructure, oil & gas, manufacturing and shipping sectors. The Special Assets Management Group is responsible for large non-performing loans and accounts under watch.

The International Business Group is responsible for ICICI Bank's international operations as well as coordinating the international strategies and alliances of its subsidiaries and affiliates.

The Corporate Centre comprises all shared services and corporate functions, including finance and secretarial, investor relations, risk management, legal, human resources and corporate branding and communications.

STRUCTURE OF IOB LIMITED

Indian Overseas Bank has been constituted as a corresponding new bank under Banking Companies (Acquisition & Transfer of Undertakings) Act 1970. The bank's Board is constituted in accordance with the Banking Companies (Acquisition & Transfer of Undertakings) Act 1970 as amended from time to time and Nationalized Banks (Management and Miscellaneous Provisions) Scheme 1970 as amended from time to time. The Board is headed by the Chairman and Managing Director who is appointed by the Central Government in consultation with the Reserve Bank of India.

Personal banking: IOB provides a wide range of products and services such as saving bank accounts, current accounts, term deposit, retail loans, home loans and mortgages, depository services, gold investment products, debit and credit cards, multi city cheque facilities, insurance and mutual funds, and real time gross settlement services.

NRI banking: It offers remittances, resident foreign currency accounts, NRI home loans and many other products for its NRI clients.

Corporate banking: IOB such as term loans and working capital loans for micro, small, and medium enterprises; and loans for professional and self employed individuals, and information technology (IT) and ITes BPO sectors, as well as NRI accounts, and Internet and mobile banking services. In addition, it provides agricultural short term loans and agric business consultancy services; and forex collection services. It also conducts government businesses like payment of direct taxes, indirect taxes, pension payment scheme, sales tax collections, provident fund scheme, etc.

Milestones: In 1964, it introduced computerization in the areas of inter-branch reconciliation and provident fund accounts. It was the first bank to venture into consumer credit by introducing a personal loan scheme. IOB was one of the 14 major banks that were nationalized in 1969.

STEPS TAKEN BY ICICI TO SUPPORT ITS FLEXIBLE AND DYNAMIC STRUCTURE

- ICICI is a company that has been recognized for a number of firsts. Notably, it was the first Indian company to list on the NYSE.
- “Mega branches” have been identified primarily on the basis of intensity and concentration of commercial banking opportunities. According to Kochhar’s emails. “These branches will deepen relationships with corporates to enhance relationship value. The heads of these branches would have adequate level of flexibility, within a defined control framework, to ensure faster customer service and decision-making at the point of origination of the transaction.” Essentially, this means more powers to the branches and decentralization of operations.
- Free from the restraints of the past, i.e., government interference, ICICI (and some of its competitors, like HDFC Bank) is bringing a new way of doing business to the financial services industry. ICICI has broken free from the socialist influence that had limited the firm’s ability to act in the best interest of its stakeholders and has been successful in targeting the top companies doing business in India as well as the potential of the growing Indian middle class.
- The financial services company has allied itself with a number of other companies in order to offer innovative services. They have partnered with Orange and Airtel to provide WAP-based m-commerce (mobile/telephone banking), with Compaq to develop a payment gateway, with Yahoo! to provide on-line financial information, and with Satyam Infoway to offer retail financial products over the Internet. ICICI and its subsidiaries have portals that allow its customers to access accounts and products on-line, offering cutting-edge web-based tools.

- ICICI was the first of the Indian financial services firms to aggressively pursue an e-commerce strategy and has established a reputation as the leader in this area. The firm has invested in the development of its e-commerce group and has dedicated resources to use their technological advantage to create better customer service and increased internal efficiencies.
- ICICI's electronic services are of the highest caliber, giving its customers access to their accounts 24-hours a day, seven days a week. ICICI has been able to guide its clients away from uniquely branch-based banking to using the more efficient and less costly computer-based banking. In some rural areas ICICI's ATMs are the only branches to which customers have access, allowing ICICI to expand into these markets without prohibitive investments in infrastructure.
- ICICI has also created a multilingual ATM network that is highly compatible with those of other banks, accepting Master, Cirrus and Maestro cards, thus giving its customers (and other users, i.e., potential customers) a high degree of ease-of-use. In addition to traditional banking functions, ICICI's ATMs are set up for paying bills and even for recharging pre-paid mobile telephones.
- ICICI has also utilized the technology of call-centers to enhance its customer service. The company has the largest call-centre in the industry and it can be accessed by customers in over one hundred cities. The service integrates automated and customer service technician services, serving a complete range of products.

STEPS TAKEN BY IOB TO SUPPORT ITS STRUCTURE

- **Global Business Performance:** The Bank was able to complete the migration process within the desired time frame. The new software once familiarized would become a back bone for efficient counter service, flexible products and sound data management which would eventually place the Bank at a higher level.
- **Income and Expenditure Analysis:** The Bank took concerted efforts to reduce the cost of deposits by shedding high cost deposits, improving Current and Savings Account (CASA) and pruning the deposit rates in line with the industry.
- **Investor Education & Protection Fund (IEPF):** Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA), Government of India has amended the Investor Education and Protection Fund (IEPF) Rules and advised the Bank the process of transfer of unpaid dividend amount to the Central Government.
- **Steps to improve Profitability:** As part of the efforts to improve profitability, bank lays renewed emphasis on improving the CASA ratio, reduction of NPAs to a large extent through intensive recovery measures like conducting frequent Lok Adalats / Recovery Camps, One-Time Settlements and resorting to legal action under SARFAESI Act in all eligible accounts.
- **Overseas Operations:** As regards our overseas operations, we have six full-fledged overseas branches – two in Hong Kong and one each in Singapore, South Korea, Sri Lanka and Thailand. Remittance Centers function in Boon Lay and Serangoon, Singapore while an Extension Counter is located in Sri Lanka. The Bank's Representative Offices are located in Guangzhou (China), Kuala Lumpur (Malaysia), Ho Chi Minh City (Vietnam) and Al Karama, (Dubai) and Bank is awaiting RBI permission for upgrading its representative offices at Dubai, Vietnam and China into full fledged branches.
- **Para banking:** In the area of Para-banking, Bank is concentrating on marketing of insurance products, sale of gold coins and IT enabled products. The Bank continues with its Corporate Agency arrangement entered into

with Universal Sompo General Insurance Company Limited (the Non–Life Insurance Joint Venture Company) for distribution of non–life insurance products.

- Corporate Governance: Corporate Governance reflects the built in value system of the Bank in conducting its day to day affairs. The Bank lays emphasis on ensuring that, structures and processes are put in place to help in compliance of the government responsibilities.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATIONS

Table 1: Showing the average values of responses for the five formalization questions

Banks	Standard operating procedures are established for covering day to day activities	Standard operating procedures are followed by the employees	Procedures are updated to reflect new circumstances	Procedures are highly efficient in most of the operations	Employees understand that procedures are based on logical concepts
IOB	4	4	4.3	4.3	3.7
ICICI	4.86	3.7	3.7	3.3	2.7

Interpretations:

Mean value for IOB= $(4+4+4.3+4.3+3.7)/5=4.06$

Mean value for ICICI= $(4.86+3.7+3.7+3.3+2.7)/5=3.6$

The larger value of mean for IOB indicates that the level of formalization is more in IOB than in ICICI. Though some extent of formalization exist in ICICI as well but rules and regulations are stricter in IOB.

From this analysis we can conclude that a public sector organization has more formalized structure than a private organization.

Table 2: Showing the average values of responses for the five decentralization questions

Banks	The employees participate in decision making process	Employees have substantial autonomy when performing their job	Many important decisions are made locally rather than centrally	Employees are involved in adding new procedures to the system	Employees are involved in updating existing procedures
IOB	2.7	3.3	2.3	3.3	3.3
ICICI	3	4.3	4	4	4

Interpretations:

Mean value for IOB= $(2.7+3.3+2.3+3.3+3.3)/5=3$

Mean value for ICICI= $(3+4.3+4+4+4)/5=3.9$

The larger value of mean for ICICI indicates that the level of decentralization is more in ICICI than in IOB. Though some extent of decentralization exists in IOB as well but power control is more distributed in ICICI.

From this analysis we can conclude that a public sector organization has more centralized structure than a private organization.

CONCLUSIONS

The structure of an organization determines the modes in which it operates and performs. Organizational structure allows the expressed allocation of responsibilities for different functions and processes to different entities such as the branch, department, workgroup and individual. A wrong organizational structure may hamper cooperation and thus hinder the completion of orders in due time and within limits of resources and budgets. Organizational structures shall be adaptive to process requirements, aiming to optimize the ratio of effort and input to output.

Though some extent of formalization exist in ICICI as well but rules and regulations are stricter in IOB. We can conclude that a public sector organization has more formalized structure than a private organization. Though some extent of decentralization exists in IOB as well but power control is more distributed in ICICI. We can conclude that a public sector organization has more centralized structure than a private organization.

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